

AI and Digital Twin Transforms in the Construction of Precision Medical Model: Healthcare Management in Smart Cities

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Abstract

In recent years, the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and digital twin (DT) is driving a new revolution in the healthcare field. Precision medical methods can utilize the complex computing techniques and models of AI, combined with various genetic and non-genetic data, to enable the system to reason and learn under the drive of data and algorithms, assisting clinical doctors and researchers in making more accurate related decisions. Research has shown that AI and DT has shown enormous technological application space in genomics, clinical cancer treatment, molecular imaging, and other fields, but it also faces potential challenges such as system bias, correlation limitations, algorithm black boxes, and unfairness. This requires the use of AI and DT transformations to build a precision medical intelligent system, which can update, capture, and study real-world data in real-time and simulate in DT. This study proposes that real-world data should be constructed from information system data and medical knowledge data from various hospitals, combined with the roles of real-world evidence (RWE), randomized clinical trial (RCT), genetic research, and AI technology in precision medicine, to innovatively design a precision medical smart system in the social 5.0 smart city. This work also proposes the structure and

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operating standards of the smart system, providing innovative ideas and contributions for the future construction of precision medical smart systems in society.

Introduction

Precision medicine is based on big data, AI, DT, cloud computing technologies to study the mechanisms of diseases caused by differences in genes, lifestyles, and environments among different patients [1-3]. By combining personalized patient environments, diagnosis and treatment situations, and genomic changes, it accurately provides personalized and standardized methods for preventing and treating major diseases [4]. Precision medicine has important value for both medicine and society [5]. The United States launched the "Precision Medicine Plan" as early as 2015, and China has also incorporated "precision medicine research and development" into its national strategy in recent years. AI and DTs transforms are changing how we create items, manage our health, and plan and operate communities, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Digitalization trend in various industries on market demand

Precision medicine is an emerging medical model developed through the cross application of biological genetic information, medical information big data, and artificial intelligence big data science [6]. Previous studies have shown that genetic science research, RWE, and prospective RCT can all improve the accuracy of clinical diagnosis and treatment [7]. At present, the data information of internet medical platforms in each place needs to be uploaded to the local regulatory unit - the Information (Data) Management Center of the Health Commission - in order to prevent data security issues, regulatory units must intervene [8]. A few alternative names for precision medicine include computational system biomedicine, system medicine, and P4 (predictive, preventative, personalized, and participative) medicine [9].

All of these words and phrases talk about the same thing: giving patients the correct treatment at the right time.

With the development of technologies such as cloud computing and biological genetics, the integration of precision medicine with RWE, RCT research, genetic science, and AI technology is becoming increasingly close. Based on the assumption framework of social 5.0 smart city, there are five main focuses of this research, as:

- This study takes the most innovative international literature in the field of precision medicine as a research case, analyzes the key points and links of RWE, RCT, and genetic research in improving precision medicine.
- Based on big data and AI technology, the overall framework of precision medicine smart system in social 5.0 smart city is constructed.
- This study starts from two directions: real-world data and medical knowledge big data, constructs a precision medical intelligent system based on RWE, RCT, and gene databases, and analyzes the logical relationships and data types of relevant parts of the intelligent system.
- We focus on the intelligent brain of precision medical intelligent systems, analyzing the structure and operating standards of the intelligent brain from different functions of its components (including research management, variable management, change management, configuration management, and release management), and clarifying the standards for real-time updating of computational data by the intelligent brain of intelligent systems.
- Finally, this study combines real-world data from the current society to simulate and analyze the improvement of clinical precision diagnosis and treatment effectiveness, ensuring that the research design of the precision medical intelligent system in this study is more accurate and effective in clinical diagnosis.

Materials and Methods

The research proposed in this article is based on the following three hypotheses:

Complex technologies in smart cities

Smart cities possess complex technologies such as highly AI and DT for data module development and combination, machine learning, and visual analysis. They can quickly develop intelligent networks, build large-scale databases in related fields, and build real-time connections with physical space.

Efficient collaboration ability

Human and computers have the ability to efficiently collaborate and solve complex new problems. People can apply mobile connectivity data, algorithms, and information networks to solve remote problems, and achieve real-time human-machine interaction communication and exchange.

Data processing ability of intelligent brain

Through AI and DT transforms, the intelligent brain of precision medicine has the ability to perform real-time and efficient data updating, collection, and reconstruction on the real world. It can discover the regular characteristics of big data such as diseases, patients, genes, and therapeutic effects in real time, and propose new research topics based on this. By combining research models and experiences of medical knowledge big data, the intelligent brain is capable of constructing new research models, collecting or changing relevant research variables, configuring research conditions, and completing innovative research.

Results

RWE and RCT

RCT is a study that establishes the relationship between baseline factors and specific clinical outcomes, which can improve the accuracy of clinical diagnosis and treatment. However, as it is an ideal evaluation study, it is difficult to form a universal treatment method. Real-world data (RWD) is the fundamental evidence for conducting precision medical research. After being collected and analyzed through AI, DT, and big data technology, RWD can form RWE that reveals the characteristics of patient lifestyle and environment, providing more accurate and effective evidence for disease prevention and treatment plans. Nevertheless, it often overlooks long-term changes in parameters such as drug toxicity and patient quality of life. Consequently, the application of RWE in precision medicine still requires a cautious attitude [10]. Although both RWE and RCT studies have their own limitations, their combined research has strong complementarity. RWE research can help determine precise diagnosis and treatment directions, providing hypothesis conditions or confirmatory basis for RCT research. For diagnostic and therapeutic methods that present positive results in RCT research, the combination of RWE research can analyze their safety and effectiveness. The combined effect of RCT and RWE research can improve the accuracy of clinical diagnosis and treatment [11]. Therefore, RCT and RWE should be the basic structure of precision medical intelligent systems. Achieving optimal health through the convergence of physical, data, and cyber domains, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Physical-Data-Cyber convergence drives precision health

Intelligent Systems

The National Institutes of Health in the United States believe that precision medicine is a scientific diagnostic and treatment method based on the study of individual genetic variability, lifestyle, and environment. In 2016, Nature released the whole genome detection research data of breast cancer, and confirmed that the gene expression of breast cancer patients is highly specific, which indicates that according to the genomics data, the disease characteristics can be significantly reflected, and the accuracy of clinical diagnosis and treatment can be improved [12], so gene research should be another infrastructure of the precision medical intelligence system. The trajectory of individual search phrases "AI & DT" and "CPS (cyber-physical system [13])" is shown by data acquired from search engine trends (Figure 3), with DT clearly showing growth from year to year.

The graph shows research interest for AI, DT and CPS from 2018 to 2023. The trend implies AI and DT is gaining attention. Trends data from Google scholar. AI, DT, and big data technology establish connections for various databases of smart systems. The use of AI and DT technology to analyze real-world medical data makes it easy to establish potential connections between individual patient genes, lifestyle, and environmental characteristics and diseases [14]. Therefore, artificial intelligence and big data technology should be used to establish connections between RWE, RCT, and gene databases in precision medical intelligence systems.

Precision medical intelligent systems

The real-world database is the data and research foundation of RWE, RCT, and gene databases. The real-world database consists of all hospital information

system diagnosis and treatment data and medical knowledge databases. The hospital information system's diagnosis and treatment data summarize the disease, diagnosis and treatment, genetic and other data of all individuals, which can reflect the patient's

disease, genetic changes, living environment and other characteristics to the greatest extent possible. It is the data or case basis for establishing RWE, RCT, and gene databases.

Figure 3. CPS and DT search interest and maturity curve since 2018.

The medical knowledge database is a summary of past precision medicine research or standards, and is the research foundation for establishing RWE, RCT, and gene databases. RWE, RCT, and gene databases use big data technology to classify and collect relevant data or research information from RWD, enabling real-time discovery of the regularity and characteristics of disease, gene, efficacy, and other data.

A smart system's intelligent brain uses AI technologies including machine learning, DT, and visual analysis to collect and analyze RWE, RCT, and gene database data, build new research models, and conduct precision

medicine research. The intelligent brain obtains new and more accurate diagnosis and treatment experiences or standards through research and analysis, and then feeds back the new diagnosis and treatment experiences or standards to the clinical practice and medical knowledge databases of various hospitals. The precision medical intelligent system updates the precision diagnosis and treatment experience and services in real time. This is the overall structure of the precision medical intelligent system in the social 5.0 smart city [15], as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Overall structure of precision medical smart systems in smart cities

Discussion

In the social 5.0 smart city, the smart brain of precision medicine utilizes AI and DT technology to conduct research, change, configuration, and other management within the smart brain. Therefore, the structure of the smart brain includes research management, variable management, change management, configuration management, and release management [16-18]. The research and operation standards for the smart brain are as follows:

Firstly, through human-machine interface (HMI), the intelligent brain issues instructions to "collect regular data of a certain type of disease in the database." Based on research experience in medical knowledge databases, the intelligent brain can analyze and determine the precision medical research direction and types of variables involved in the disease. Through machine learning and other technologies, new research variables and models are constructed. The research results provide hypothetical conditions and confirmatory support for RCT research, and this process is for research management.

Secondly, variable management determines the research model and variable types based on research management. Meanwhile, based on the research information provided by research management, configuration management utilizes AI technology to construct research models and RCT research

conditions, and variable management must comply with the research models, conditions, or requirements of configuration management. Once again, when variable management does not fully comply with configuration management requirements, configuration management construction fails. The intelligent brain transfers all research models, variables, conditions, etc. to change management for testing and updating, and manages the addition, reduction, or reconstruction of research models or variable data until variable management meets configuration management requirements.

Finally, change management will transfer the updated research model, variables, and conditions to release management. After the release management verifies and matches the model and variables, it will be transferred to configuration management for research. After completing the research according to the research model and relevant conditions, the configuration management will feed back the research results to the research management again [19-20]. The research management will extract the results into clinical practice diagnosis and treatment standards or medical knowledge experience, and the intelligent brain will provide feedback to the clinical practice or medical knowledge database of each hospital, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Intelligent brain structure and operating standards of precision medical intelligent system

Conclusion

The application of AI and DT in precision medicine is a rapidly developing field. As a major participant in AI and precision medicine on the international stage, world clearly encourages the application of AI and DT technology in precision medicine and other fields. This study is very important for building a precision medical smart system in society 5.0. By analyzing the research factors that affect precision medicine and the application of AI, DT, and big data technology, a precision medical framework and its smart brain structure and operating standards in Society 5.0 smart cities have been constructed. By combining the research advantages of RWE, RCT, and genetic science, and tracking and analyzing the causes of diseases, genetic changes, and other factors over a long period of time, we can deeply explore the relationship mechanism between human diseases and genes, environment, etc. This study construct disease prediction and early warning models, especially for infectious diseases and major diseases, optimize human disease prediction analysis, and provide precise prevention and intervention treatment for diseases.

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Conflict of Interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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